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Assessment of the socio-economic indicators of the railway transport enterprise in the context of the strategic development of the country's economy and analysis of its results

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Annotation

In the context of the strategic development of the country's economy, the transport system, especially the railway transport network, is of particular importance. As an important infrastructural link of the national economy, this sector is important in ensuring the continuity of production processes, supporting export-import operations, strengthening interregional economic ties, and developing domestic market integration.

Key words:

singular economics, applied economics, railway transport.

Stable and efficient operation of railway transport not only increases the reliability of the logistics system, but also directly affects the rates of economic growth, the level of transport costs and the balance of regional development. In this regard, the scientific assessment and analysis of the socio-economic indicators of railway transport enterprises is one of the priority areas of modern economic policy.

The relevance of this issue is determined, first of all, by the need to deeply study, along with the economic efficiency of the activities of railway transport enterprises, their social effectiveness. In particular, a comprehensive assessment of factors such as the level of utilization of production resources, labor productivity, employment indicators, quality of services, social protection of employees and the level of satisfaction of the population with transport services makes it possible to determine the real state of this

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industry. At the same time, the issues of introducing digital technologies, using energy-efficient management mechanisms, ensuring environmental safety and adapting to the principles of a green economy in the strategic development of railway transport enterprises are also becoming increasingly relevant.

In today's conditions of globalization and increasing economic competition, the assessment of socio-economic indicators of railway transport enterprises is important not only for determining domestic economic efficiency, but also for revealing the overall transport potential and integration capabilities of the country. Based on a systematic analysis of the activities of this sector, it is possible to draw the necessary scientific and practical conclusions for improving state transport policy, increasing management efficiency in the sector, enhancing investment attractiveness, and developing long-term sustainable development strategies.

Despite the high share of transport services in Uzbekistan's exports of services in 2014-2024, the overall trend has been downward. If in 2014 this figure was 57.71 percent, then in 2018 it fell to 45.61 percent, in 2019 to 40.03 percent, and in 2022 it decreased to 34.52 percent. Although a certain recovery was observed in 2023 to 38.15 percent, in 2024 it decreased again to 33.33 percent. This situation can be explained by several factors: firstly, the share of other types of services in the structure of services exports, in particular travel, information and communication, financial and business services, may be increasing; secondly, the redistribution of international transport flows and increased competition in transit routes; third, the geoeconomic situation, changes in demand in external markets, and fluctuations in logistics costs affected the share of transport services (Table 3.1).

The overall competitiveness of countries according to the TTDI indicators is largely closely related to their transport infrastructure readiness, especially the land transport system. Here, Kazakhstan, ranked 52nd, recorded one of the best results in the

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region, with an important role played by its land and port infrastructure at 3.14, air transport infrastructure at 2.82, and tourism services infrastructure at 3.64. The relatively high level of land infrastructure among these indicators means that the railway network and internal territorial connectivity in Kazakhstan are one of the main pillars supporting tourism. Azerbaijan also ranks high at 56th place, and its air transport infrastructure seems to be quite strong at 4.29, but its land and port infrastructure is not bad at 2.83. This means that Azerbaijan is using a more multimodal model in its tourism competitiveness, that is, air and land transport work together. Armenia, Moldova, Tajikistan and the Kyrgyz Republic have lower land infrastructure indicators, which negatively affected their tourism rankings. So, the table itself shows that tourism competitiveness is determined not only by cultural or natural resources, but also by the quality of railways, roads and other land transport systems that take tourists from destination to destination. The country ranks lower than Armenia at 78th place and an index of 4.06, but higher than Moldova, Tajikistan and the Kyrgyz Republic. Uzbekistan’s strongest point is its business environment (6.17), which is one of the highest scores in the table. Security (5.00), human resources and labor market (5.02), and openness to tourism (5.49) are also not bad. However, the fact that Uzbekistan’s land and port infrastructure is at 1.45 is a very important signal. Because this indicator is low compared to many countries in the table, and it is this factor that is seen as one of the main links that lower the country’s overall tourism competitiveness. From a railway perspective, this means that although Uzbekistan has tourist potential, historical cities, and openness, the high-quality railway service system connecting them, the quality of station logistics, intermodal connectivity, the convenience of regional routes, and service infrastructure have not yet been sufficiently transformed into a competitive advantage. However, Uzbekistan's tourism model can be strengthened precisely by railways, since the potential for turning such centers as Samarkand, Bukhara, Tashkent,

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Khiva, and Kokand into a single tourist route based on railways is higher than in many countries in the region.

Kazakhstan's advantage over Uzbekistan is clearly felt not only in the overall rating, but also in terms of its ground infrastructure: Kazakhstan has 3.14, while Uzbekistan has 1.45. This difference is more than double. Therefore, the level of development of the railway and general ground transport network can be considered an important factor in explaining Kazakhstan's better position in the TTDI rating. Although Uzbekistan has a stronger business environment compared to Azerbaijan, some weaknesses remain in its transport and service infrastructure. Compared to Armenia, Uzbekistan has a good business environment and some openness indicators, but infrastructure constraints prevent it from moving up. Compared to Tajikistan and the Kyrgyz Republic, Uzbekistan has a stronger institutional and market environment, but this advantage would be even more pronounced if it fully developed a railway-based tourism chain.

The analysis of production and technical and economic indicators shows that the efficiency of using fixed assets and labor resources at Uzbekistan Railways JSC has developed in a relatively positive direction. The fact that the renewal coefficient of fixed assets has remained in the range of 0.8–1.0 in almost all years and reached 1.0 in 2020, 2022, 2024 and 2025 indicates that the company has a practice of modernizing its production base and regularly updating fixed assets. This is a very important strategic advantage, given the high capital capacity of the railway network. The increase in labor productivity from 150744.9 in 2017 to 281614.0 in 2023 indicates a significant improvement in the efficiency of using labor resources at the enterprise; After a decline in 2024, its increase to 245,000.0 in 2025 indicates that the overall trend is still positive. The fund value indicator, which has remained around 0.5 for many years and increased to 0.7 in 2023, indicates a short-term activation in the return on production funds and

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the efficiency of their use. The fact that employee turnover is mainly around 1.0 indicates a relatively stable staff composition, while the indicator of 0.9 in 2023 may indicate a relatively increased effectiveness of the personnel retention policy. In terms of energy efficiency, the share of energy costs in the cost of production increased from 0.10–0.11 in 2017–2021 to 0.12 in 2022 indicates that energy resource costs are under certain pressure.

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